

Whole-genome sequences of two *Bacillus velezensis* strains associated with the roots of fruit trees

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Abstract

This study reports the complete and annotated genome assemblies of two plant-associated *Bacillus velezensis* strains 31 and 173 originating from the rhizosphere of apple and mulberry trees, respectively. These genome sequences serve to enrich the current array of genomic data and offer a perspective into essential and/or unique genes pivotal for their plant growth promotion, and their effectiveness in biocontrol against plant pathogens.

Introduction

Some *Bacillus* species, classified as plant growth promoting bacteria, are used as an eco-friendly alternatives to chemical pesticides and fertilizers. Within the *Bacillus* genus, different strains of *Bacillus velezensis*, have received considerable attention (Fan et al., 2018; Fazle Rabbee and Baek, 2020; Platel et al., 2021). This species is considered as a model species for plant-associated bacilli providing benefits to its host in terms of growth promotion and protection against phytopathogens (Andrić et al., 2023). *B. velezensis* differentiates from other species by devoting more than 10% of its genome to gene clusters responsible for the synthesis of specialized metabolites (Grubbs et al., 2017; Harwood et al., 2018). This secondary metabolome is chemically diverse and includes volatile compounds, bacteriocins and a range of non-ribosomally synthesized polyketides and lipopeptides (Fan et al., 2018; Yousfi et al., 2024). Some of these compounds are unique to the species *velezensis*, conferring this latter an adaptive advantage in specific ecological niches.

Despite their success, a better understanding of the mechanisms governing plant-beneficial effects mediated by these living microbes is essential to improve the efficacy and robustness of

treatments. This task is challenging with classic screening methods based on *in vitro* tests. The comprehensive analysis provided by whole-genome sequencing offers a valuable approach for the identification of all genes in the beneficial bacterium and their predicted function, allowing one to predict potential benefits between the plant and the bacterium (Larena et al., 2023). This predictive tool can lead to a more successful selection of potential beneficial microbes as it can serve for deducing potential structures of the resultant natural product (Bauman et al., 2021), enabling the discovery of new bioactive metabolites and the differentiation of metabolites within a strain collection (Guo et al., 2020). In addition, it allows for categorizing genes linked to plant growth-promoting activities, simultaneously shedding light on their molecular and operational mechanisms (Guo et al., 2020).

In this study, we present the whole genome sequencing of two plant-associated bacteria 31 and 173 isolated from rhizospheric soil (unpublished data). These bacterial strains were selected based on their demonstrated antibacterial activity against several bacterial phytopathogens.

Material and Methods

Bacterial isolates

Strains 31 and 173 were isolated from Tunisian rhizosphere soil of apple and mulberry trees, respectively. Bacterial strains were isolated according to the procedure described by Frikha-Gargouri et al. (2017).

Sequencing of bacterial genomic DNA

Bacterial culturing and DNA extraction were conducted by microbesNG following to their established protocols (<https://microbesng.com>). DNA processing was carried out using a sequencing service provider named MicrobesNG (Birmingham, UK, <https://microbesng.com>). DNA quantification and library preparation were performed by a Hamilton Microlab STAR automated liquid handling system (Hamilton Bonaduz AG, Switzerland). Libraries were prepared using the Nextera XT Library Prep Kit (Illumina, San Diego, USA) following the manufacturer's instructions with the following modifications: the amount of input DNA was increased 2-fold, and the PCR elongation time was increased to 45 seconds. Genomic DNA libraries were sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, USA) using a 250 bp paired-end protocol.

The reads were subjected to trimming using Trimmomatic version 0.30 (Bolger et al., 2014) with a sliding window quality cutoff of Q15. De novo assembly was performed on samples

using SPAdes version 3.7 (Bankevich et al., 2012), and contigs were annotated using Prokka 1.11 (Seemann, 2014).

Results

Genomic Features

The genomic features for both strains 31 and 173 are summarized in table 1. The genomes of these bacterial strains were estimated at 4,052,389 bp and 4,021,565 bp with 110 and 92× mean coverage, respectively. The genomic GC contents are 46.27% for strain 31 and 46.44% for strain 173. The genome of strain 31 harbors 3868 protein coding genes; while 3919 genes were predicted for strain 173.

Nucleotides sequences accession numbers

Whole genome sequences for *B. velezensis* strains 31 and 173 have been deposited into NCBI GenBank under accession numbers GCA_033194935.1 and GCA_032841655.1, respectively. Raw reads are also available on the NCBI SRA database under the run numbers SRR26351690 for *B. velezensis* strain 31 and SRR26301746 for *B. velezensis* strain 173 (Table 1).

Table1: Genomic features of *B. velezensis* strains 31 and 173.

Bacterial species	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	
Strain	31	173
Genome size (bp)	4,052,389	4,021,565
% GC	46.27	46.44
Number of contigs (>=1000 bp)	30	20
Largest contig (bp)	443388	1089039
Mean coverage (X)	110.526	92.4704
Number of reads	941777	771977
N50 (bp)	307650	1029991
Protein-coding gene	3868	3919
tRNA number	83	86
tmRNA number	1	1
SRA accession numbers	SRR26351690	SRR26301746
Assemblies accession numbers	GCA_033194935.1	GCA_032841655.1

Statement on continuing work

The datasets are being made available before their formal publication and should be considered as preliminary. We welcome feedback from the community. Please contact OFG (olfafrikhagargouri2@gmail.com) for further information.

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